

**DOCUMENTATION OF PERFORMANCE STYLES IN YORUBA DUNDUN
DRUMMING**

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Abstract

It is an established fact that indigenous knowledge precedes colonization and any creativity in musical arts is traced to indigenous system of African music making. One cannot deny the fact that some efforts have been made in the past to integrate aspects of collectivism in musical arts but the truth remains that creativity in its whole is yet to be fully explored by the present generation, especially, in the area of performance within instrumental ensemble. In those days, indigenous performance style of drumming have specific styles such that whenever it is played, people around understand the style and dancer knows exactly what to dance to it; but presently, it is observed that the lead instrumentalists of many traditional performance on drums are not actually identified with any particular style due to little or no knowledge they possess about the instrument they are handling. Therefore, this paper intends to document indigenous styles of drumming pattern of dundun drum by showcasing the musical scoring of some of these indigenous styles for proper documentation of Yoruba culture; believing that it will expose more roles and the indigenous styles of playing dundun drum in typical Yoruba way, and also enlighten the 21st century traditional performer of dundun drum on the co-ordination of traditional ensemble. The writer uses documentary, historical method, unstructured interviews, and participant observation to source for data for the paper. In conclusion the paper traced the origin of indigenous knowledge in music performance in Yoruba land, and the performance style of dundun pattern culturally and also recommends the possible ways of preserving and expanding this knowledge.